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2. HEALTH EFFECTS OF AMBIENT FINE PARTICULATE MATTER (PM_{2.5}) IN SERBIA

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Objectives: The overall aim of this work is to estimate the health effects of ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in Serbia, specifically, quantify the mortality potentially associated with air pollution.

Methods: Exposure data for Serbia were obtained from European Environmental Agency. The population weighted average exposure in Serbia was 23.9 (SD 5.2) µg/m³. Health effects were assessed using population attributable fraction methods (PAF) for PM_{2.5} at national and district level. Deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} exposures were calculated in national level using WHO Global Health Estimates 2015 data for background natural cause mortality for 30+ years of age for Serbia and Health Statistical Yearbook of Republic of Serbia 2015 for mortality data in district level (not available for Kosovo).

Results: Lowest calculated PAF was in North Banat (10.0%) and the highest was in Kosovo districts (15.4%). Total of 13,600 (PAF=13.4%) deaths in Serbia in 2015 were attributable to air pollution. According to district the range of attributable deaths were from 206 (Toplica) to 2718 (Belgrade).

Conclusion: In total 13,600 deaths were attributable to PM_{2.5} exposure in Serbia. District distribution of PAF shows that the lowest PAF was in the north Serbia while the highest one was in the South.

Keywords: Particulate Matter, Mortality, Serbia